

IN-SITU ALUMINIUM MATRIX COMPOSITE PREPARED BY ULTRASONIC VIBRATION

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ABSTRACT

A novel in-situ process was presented in this paper, which in-situ Al matrix composite can be fabricated easily and inexpensively by means of ultrasonic vibration accompanying with an exothermic reaction between titanium oxide whisker and molten aluminium alloy (Al-6%Mg and Al-4Cu%-1.5Mg%). The metallography investigation and x-ray diffraction analysis showed that the phases were $TiAl_3$, $MgAl_2O_4$, MgO and Al in the TiO_2/Al -Mg system and $TiAl_3$, MgO, $MgAl_2O_4$, $CuAl_2$ and Al in the TiO_2/Al -Cu-Mg system with the sizes of the oxides were less than $1\mu m$. The microhardness values of the matrix, the range reinforced by fine oxides particles and $TiAl_3$ intermetallic phase were 71, 210 and 320, respectively. The similar results were obtained with $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker instead of TiO_2 whisker. The process of TiO_2/Al reaction squeeze casting was also studied in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMC) are commonly obtained through the addition of appropriate second phases to metal matrixes. This type of MMCs is suffered from significant difficulties associated with their processing and fabricating in mixing or combining the reinforcing phases with the matrixes and in controlling the nature of interfaces and interphases between the matrixes and reinforcements. Such composite generally cost expensively as a result of high raw materials cost and high composite processing cost that have limited their use. In-situ metal or ceramic matrix composites whose reinforcements are formed in-situ in the matrixes have good interface compatibilities and wettabilities between matrixes and reinforcements. In-situ technologies have offered the potential for overcoming most of the difficulties in processing and fabrication and for reducing their cost to acceptable levels. So there are growing interests in the study of the in-situ techniques to fabricate metal, intermetallic and ceramic matrix composites, such as Lanxide process [1,2], XDTM technology [3] and reaction squeeze casting [4]. Lanxide process can be divided into two kinds. One is the direct metal oxidation process (called DIMOX) by which a dense in-situ Al_2O_3/Al composite body being produced through the oxidation

of an aluminium alloy by a gaseous oxidant e.g. air[1]. This process relies on a change in relative surface energies with certain alloy elements (Mg,Si) added to aluminium to promote wettability of Al_2O_3 with molten aluminium. The net-shape or near-net-shape parts can be form directly using this method. Another is the pressureless metal infiltration process (called PRIMEX) which is mainly for fabricating metal matrix composites by the spontaneous infiltration of filler preform with molten aluminium alloy. This process relies on the use of an aluminium alloy containing Mg element and a nitrogen-containing atmosphere. Increase of the infiltrating temperature and magnesium content results in increase of infiltration rates. In the process of XDTM which was developed by Martin Marietta Corporation, the elemental components of various reinforcing phases are mixed with or incorporated into the metallic or intermetallic matrix materials. After heating the mixture to a high temperature typically above the melting point of the matrix or to a point where a self-propagating reaction can take place, the elemental constituents react exothermically to form a dispersed reinforcing particulates in-situ in the matrix. The XDTM materials are usually used as a starting materials. The final parts are made by secondary working this materials using conventional metal-working methods. In the process of reaction squeeze casting, the reinforcement preform is infiltrated by molten metal at a temperature above the starting point of the reaction between the reinforcement and metal under the action of applied pressure, so the reaction and infiltration occur simultaneously with the reaction heat releasing to maintain the reaction during the course of squeeze casting. The microstructure of the composite is usually inhomogeneous because the beginning time as well as the degree of the reaction are varied in different part of the preform.

It is well known that power ultrasound has positive effects on cleaning and polishing a working part surface, dispersing fine particles in liquid homogeneously, improving the wettability between a solid and a liquid and accelerating a chemical reaction because a high-intensity ultrasound can produce a cavitation effect in the liquid. Therefore ultrasonic technology is widely used in mechanical and chemical industry and in medicine engineering. Power ultrasound has been used successfully to fabricate continuous SiC reinforcing aluminium composite by the present authors group[5], and to improve the wettability of a non-wetting Al_2O_3 fiber/molten aluminium system to attain full infiltration with a low applied pressure[6]. In this paper, a novel in-situ process based on the cavitation effect of high-intensity ultrasound is presented. In-situ Al matrix composite is obtained by using this method accompanying an exothermic reaction between TiO_2 or $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker and molten aluminium alloy. The ultrasonic vibration is transmitted to a liquid through a direct contact of the step-horn with liquid and produces a cavitation effect in it. To understand the mechanism of the reaction, the process of reaction squeeze casting using TiO_2/Al system to fabricate in-situ Al_2O_3/Al composite and the differential thermal analysis of the squeeze casting sample are also presented. The microstructures and phases of two kinds samples prepared by ultrasonic vibrating and reaction squeeze casting respectively are compared by means of metallography and x-ray diffraction.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The ultrasonic vibration system consisted of an oscillator and a step horn. The step-horn made of titanium was utilized to gain a longitudinal vibration amplitude and to protect the oscillator from molten metal. The ultrasound is transmitted into a metal liquid through a direct contact of the step-horn with liquid. The amplitude at the end surface

of step-horn increased with the increase of the ultrasonic power.

Titanium oxide whiskers of the diameter of about $1\mu\text{m}$ were supplied as a reactive substance and commercially pure aluminium with 99.8% purity, Al-6%Mg and Al-1.5%Mg-4%Cu aluminium alloys were selected as another reactive substances and matrixes. The TiO_2 whisker preform was prepared in such a way that the whiskers were disentangled with ultrasonic vibrating in water and pressed into a quasi-shape block. Preform was dried at 200°C for 24 hours and its volume fraction of whisker was about 0.2. Being putted into the molten aluminium suffered from ultrasonic vibrating, the preform was splited by ultrasonic vibrating at first, then infiltrated and wetted by the melt and finally reacted with aluminium melt pressurelessly under the action of the cavitation effect of high-intensity ultrasound. The temperature of molten aluminium was 750°C . The time and degree of the reaction between TiO_2 preform and aluminium varied with the difference of the alloy contents of aluminium. Vibrated for certain time, the whiskers were consumed and the molten metal was reinforced by reacted solid compounds. So the in-situ aluminium composites were fabricated.

To understand the mechanism of the reaction, determine the ultrasonic vibrating technological parameters and compare the microstructures of the samples, the reaction squeeze casting process was also investigated using the commercially pure Al and TiO_2 whiskers as raw materials. The temperatures of molten aluminium, preform and dies were 750°C , 800°C and 400°C respectively. The TiO_2/Al composite was fabricated under the pressure of 100 MPa without obvious infiltration defects.

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) test with the temperature arising rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ by means of Japan Rigaku DTA machine and a heat-treatment at 800°C for 5min were done for the sample made by squeeze casting. The microstructures of the two kinds composites prepared by power ultrasound and squeeze casting respectively were observed and compared with a metallograph microscope or a scanning electronic microscope and a x-ray diffraction machine. The x-ray diffraction were carried out with Cu target and Ni filter at the condition of 35 KV and 35 mA using Japan Rigaku D/max-IIIa diffraction machine. The microhardness values were also tested under the load of 50g loading for 10s.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS (DTA)

The DTA curve of TiO_2/Al sample was shown in Fig.1. There were two peaks related to phases transitions. The endothermic peaks appearing in the range of $640\text{-}680^\circ\text{C}$ was related to aluminium phase transition from solid to liquid. The exothermic peak appearing in the range of $710\text{-}770^\circ\text{C}$ was related to the deoxidization reaction between TiO_2 and Al. According to thermodynamics and differential thermal analysis (DTA), the equation of the reaction can be written as:

The phases Ti_xAl_y were TiAl , TiAl_3 and Ti_3Al according to the reaction condition.

Fig.1 The DTA curve of TiO₂/Al sample

STUDIES OF REACTION SQUEEZE CASTING

The optimal metallograph photos of the as-fabricated or heat-treatment samples obtained by squeeze casting process were shown in Fig.2. The x-ray diffraction results were listed in table 1.

Fig. 2 The optical metallograph photos of squeeze casting samples.

(a) As fabricated; (b) After heat treatment

During the process of squeeze casting, the temperature of molten aluminium was so low and the time of aluminium liquid in contact with TiO₂ preform was so short that Al and TiO₂ could not react and the added reinforcement remained its original shape (e.g. whisker) in the composite. The preforme was infiltrated by molten aluminium without reaction. After the sample heated at 800°C for 10min. at the protection of Ar gas with 5L/min gas flow, the reaction took place according to the DTA result. The heated sample became brittle with its microhardness being 580, which was close to the value of TiAl₃ intermetallic. The x-ray diffraction analysis showed that the TiO₂/Al composite had become an intermetallic matrix composite reinforced by in-situ α -Al₂O₃ particles. If the temperature of molten aluminium was raised above 800°C in the process of squeeze casting, the exothermic reaction would take place accompanying with the infiltrating of metal liquid to the preform during the course, then the in-situ Al matrix composite was fabricated with inhomogenous microstructure.

Table 1 The x-ray diffraction analysis results of the samples

matrix	process	state	phases
Al	S.Q	as-fabricated	TiO ₂ ,Al
Al	S.Q	heated	α -Al ₂ O ₃ ,TiAl ₃ ,Ti ₃ Al,Al
Al-Mg	U.V	as-fabricated	MgO,MgAl ₂ O ₄ ,TiAl ₃ ,Al
Al-Cu-Mg	U.V	as-fabricated	MgO,MgAl ₂ O ₄ ,TiAl ₃ ,CuAl ₂ ,Al

SAMPLE ANALYSIS

When the TiO₂ preform was putted into molten aluminium subjected to power ultrasound for a certain time, the preform depleted in the matrix then reacted with the melt. The samples of the reacted aluminium liquids containing different alloy elements were observed by a scanning electrical microscopy and a optical microscopy. The microstructures of these samples were shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3. The microstructure of ultrasonic vibrating in-situ Al matrix composite. (a) TiO₂/Al-6%Mg; (b) TiAl₃ in Al-6%Mg; (c) TiO₂/pure Al; (d) TiO₂/Al-4%Cu-1.5%Mg

The results of x-ray diffraction analysis of these samples were also listed in table 1. For TiO₂ and pure aluminium system, there were some black pieces with irregular shape in the matrix. The x-ray diffraction analysis showed that there was no reaction taking place between TiO₂ whisker and pure aluminium. The preform was just broken by ultrasound and dispersed in the metal. With the matrix containing Mg element, e.g. Al-6%Mg and Al-4%Cu-1.5%Mg aluminium alloys, the reaction between the whisker and matrix was carried out perfectly and the temperature of the molten aluminium arised with the release of the reaction heat. There were two kinds of reacted compounds: one was fine particle

with the size less than $1\ \mu\text{m}$ and another was gray phase with regular shape and the size about tens microns. The x-ray diffraction analysis showed that the phases were TiAl_3 , MgAl_2O_4 , MgO and Al in the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Al-Mg}$ composite, and TiAl_3 , MgO , MgAl_2O_4 , CuAl_2 and Al in the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Al-Cu-Mg}$ composite. It was proved that the following reaction between TiO_2 and Al matrix containing Mg element was carried out perfectly in the process of ultrasonic vibrating.

The microhardness values of the aluminium matrix, the range reinforced by fine particles and gray phase were 71, 210 and 320, respectively. It was concluded that the fine particles were MgO and MgAl_2O_4 , and the regular gray phase was TiAl_3 . In Al-Cu-Mg matrix, there were some long narrow pieces of CuAl_2 phase in the matrix. The similar results were obtained with $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 0.6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker instead of TiO_2 whisker.

STUDIES OF ULTRASONIC VIBRATING REACTION

It was found that the whisker preform would not react with aluminium melt even at the temperature of the melt higher than the reaction beginning point (e.g. 750°C) because of the preform was not wetted and infiltrated by the melt without the action of power ultrasonic vibration. When an ultrasonic energy was introduced into a liquid, a temporary negative pressure arised in some liquid regions, which induced an excessive tensile stress to creat bubbles or voids in these regions. Those bubbles oscillated under the action of ultrasonic field unsteadily. If the negative pressure exceeded a certain value, the bubbles expanded rapidly and collapsed or imploded subsequently at a high speed. At the same time, a rather substantial compressive shock wave formed and propagated through the liquid. This phenomenon is called the cavitation effect of high-intensity ultrasound[7], whose action was to create a high pressure and a high temperature in the cavitation acted reigons when the bubbles collapsed. When TiO_2 preform was putted into aluminium melt, the air brought into the melt by the preform and the gas dissolved in the melt was the cavitation nuclei. If some of those bubbles collapsed, a high pressure and a high temperature was created around the individual whisker, which was favourable for improving the wettability and accelarating the reaction between the whisker and the melt.

During the ultrasonic vibrating process, the reaction rate changed with the differences of the contents of alloy elements in molten aluminium. As observed above, the TiO_2 could not be wetted and reacted by pure Al . The reason why the exothermic reaction was not induced by ultrasonic vibration was that there was a dense Al_2O_3 oxide film on the surface of the aluminium melt which resisted their contacting and reacting, and that the Al_2O_3 oxide film could not be spoiled by current ultrasonic power. The reaction could take place by increasing of the ultrasonic energy to deplete the oxide film. When the melt contained Mg element, the oxide film on the surface of aluminium was loose with some microchannals which let aluminium through them. On the other hand, Mg improved the wettability of TiO_2 whisker and the melt. So the exothermic reaction was carried out to produce some new in-situ reinforcements to reinforcing the metal.

It was proved that the ultrasonic vibrating process could fabricate in-situ Al matrix composite reinforced by oxides particles and intermetallic compounds. The V_f of reinforcements could be controlled by changing the amount of TiO_2 . The ultrasonic vibrating process was a low cost technique to fabricate reacted in-situ composites. Other in-situ

composites could also be made by changing reaction systems using this process. With $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker instead of TiO_2 whisker, the ultrasonic vibrating reaction also took place and the microstructures of these in-situ composites were similar. In addition, the crystallization defects shown in Fig.3 were eliminated by hot squeezing.

CONCLUSIONS

By studying the ultrasonic vibration reaction and reaction squeeze casting, it could be concluded that:

(1). TiO_2 preform would not react with pure aluminium melt during the process of squeeze casting when the temperature of the preform and melt were lower than the reaction beginning point. After heating the TiO_2/Al sample at $800^\circ C$ for 5min., the reaction took place and the sample became an in-situ intermetallic matrix composite.

(2). The TiO_2 whisker preform could be broken, then wetted and reacted directly with the aluminium melt containing Mg element under the action of ultrasonic vibration. The dense oxide film on the surface of molten pure aluminium resisted the reaction between the whisker and the melt. By increasing the ultrasonic energy transmitted to the melt, this dense oxide film could be depleted by vibrating and the reaction could be carried out.

(3). The in-situ reinforcements were oxide particles with the size less than $1\mu m$ and $TiAl_3$ intermetallic with the size about tens microns in the ultrasonic vibrating process. The microhardness of the in-situ aluminium was higher significantly than that of the matrix. Changing the reaction system, other in-situ metal matrix composite could be fabricated by this process inexpensively and easily.

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